

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS ON CHINA'S GREEN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT MECHANISM

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ABSTRACT

In the context of the global resource crisis and environmental degradation, the development of green economy is an inevitable choice as a basic national policy to break the bottleneck of traditional economic development and promote the construction of ecological civilization in my country. This article introduces the staged achievements of China's green economy, such as the country's strengthening of top-level design, the implementation of the "dual carbon" goal, the scale of green production continues to grow, and the green lifestyle is deeply rooted in the hearts of the people. It also discusses the current challenges facing the development of the green economy. Realistic problems, such as the dominance of developed countries in the market, making it difficult for China to have a voice, insufficient independent innovation capabilities, difficulty in digesting the frictional costs of transformation, unreasonable structure of the three industries, and difficulty in transformation, etc. Finally, relevant countermeasures and suggestions for developing green economy in the new era are proposed. I hope Provide effective suggestions for the country to transform into a green economy and achieve high-quality development.

Keywords: Green economy: Development status: Realistic problems: Countermeasures and suggestions.

INTRODUCTION

China has made great achievements in green economy, but it faces the problems of ecological destruction and high energy consumption, and needs to take a new path of industrialization. Green economy can promote people to change their energy utilization and lifestyle, carry out technological and institutional innovation, and move towards ecological civilization. Global warming is very harmful, causing natural disasters, economic losses and casualties. According to statistics, in the past 30 years (1990-2019), 91.6% of major natural disasters, 67.6% of deaths due to disasters, 83.7% of economic losses and 92.4% of insurance losses in the world were caused by meteorological and its secondary and derivative disasters, as shown in Figure 1 [1]. China's rapid industrialization consumes a lot of energy and emits a lot of greenhouse gases, and it must seek a more environmentally friendly production model. Taking oil and water resources as examples, China's oil production in 2022 will be 199 million tons, a year-on-year increase of 2.1%, and consumption will be 720

million tons, a year-on-year increase of 4.1%; the total water consumption in 2022 will be 592.02 billion m², an increase of 10.73 billion m² compared with 2020 [2]. Capitalist industrial production suppresses the rights of nature, causes environmental pollution, and sacrifices the long-term interests of mankind. Human beings must reflect on the capitalist mode of production and consumption, solve the ecological dilemma, establish a sustainable economic system, and adopt renewable energy. The green economy must develop ecological agriculture and improve agricultural output efficiency. According to data released by the Ministry of Agriculture, by the end of 2022, China has more than 150 national ecological agriculture demonstration counties, which have driven more than 600 provincial ecological agriculture demonstration counties and built more than 3,000 ecological agriculture demonstration sites. The green economy is conducive to the establishment of a harmonious ecology and promotes the establishment of an environmentally friendly society.

Figure 1. Percentage of natural disasters and economic losses in the past 30 years

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. China's current economic development

1.1 Take top-level design as the guide and strengthen policy support

The Chinese government has always attached great importance to environmental protection and resource conservation and utilization, and actively promoted the formulation and implementation of policies related to ecological protection. For example, at the beginning of 2021, the State Council has issued documents such as the "Guiding Opinions on Accelerating the Establishment and Improvement of a Green, Low-Carbon, Circular Development Economic System" to actively promote the development of the green economy. For example, in September 2020, President Xi Jinping delivered a speech at the general debate of the 75th United Nations General Assembly, establishing the "dual carbon" goal of striving to peak carbon dioxide emissions before 2030 and achieving carbon neutrality before 2060. At the same time, the government has promulgated a series of policy measures to ensure that the "dual carbon" goals are achieved on schedule. At present, my country has established a "1+N" policy system for carbon peak and carbon neutrality: in September 2021, the "Opinions of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China and the State Council on Fully, Accurately and Comprehensively Implementing the New Development Concept and Doing a Good Job in Carbon Peak and Carbon Neutrality" was promulgated, followed by the promulgation of the "Action Plan for Carbon Peaking before 2030", which together constitute the top-level design, and gradually improve various key areas, key industries and related support and guarantee systems, such as the "14th Five-Year Plan for Industrial Green Development", "Carbon Peak Implementation Plan in the Industrial Field", "Carbon Peak Implementation Plan in the Building Materials Industry", "Science and Technology Support for Carbon Peak and Carbon Neutrality Implementation Plan (2022-2030)", "Opinions on Financial Support for Carbon Peaking and Carbon Neutrality" and other policy

documents. 31 provinces (autonomous regions and municipalities) have formulated and completed carbon peak implementation plans.

1.2 Let the data speak for itself, and the implementation of the "double carbon" goal has achieved remarkable results

Since the national carbon trading market went online for more than 2 years in July 2021, transaction volume has gradually grown steadily and orderly. In July 2022, the national carbon market completed its first stock contract cycle, encouraging the advanced and eliminating the backward. Enterprises' awareness of emission reduction has been improved, and the incentive and restraint effect of the carbon market has initially emerged. As of the end of February 2023, the cumulative transaction volume of carbon emission quotas reached 232 million tons, and the cumulative transaction volume reached 10.59 billion yuan. The torch fuel at the 2022 Beijing Winter Olympics will use hydrogen energy, and the buses that transport athletes and staff will also use hydrogen energy to achieve green emissions. The power supply for the venues in the three competition areas will reach 100%, making the Beijing Winter Olympics the first The "carbon neutral" Winter Olympics, its green attributes are also recorded in the annals of history.

The realization of the "dual carbon" goal focuses on enterprises. Large carbon emission enterprises are actively deploying emission reduction plans. Central enterprises have formulated carbon peak action plans based on "one enterprise, one policy". Large enterprises are also planning environmental protection plans for the entire product life cycle. For example, Moutai Group has implemented five major projects, namely "increasing water, improving air quality, conserving soil, protecting microorganisms, and balancing the ecosystem", to accelerate green, low-carbon and circular development with practical measures. In order to support the development of green, low-carbon infrastructure and related enterprises, the state has given priority financial support. By the end of 2022, as shown in Figure 2 [3].

Figure 2: China's green economy investment and resource transformation ratio

In 2022, global carbon dioxide emissions from energy consumption and industrial processes increased by 0.9%, while China's energy-related emissions decreased by 0.2%. This was due to the impact of the new coronavirus infection on production, but overall, the reduction in China's carbon dioxide emissions contributed to the slow growth of global carbon dioxide emissions and reduced global industrial emissions [4].

1.3 Eco-friendly and environmentally friendly enterprises are growing stronger, and green production methods are developing in a positive direction

In recent years, government departments have made a series of efforts to promote the greening of production methods. In order to better guide the green transformation of the manufacturing industry and play a demonstration role in leading the whole, the Ministry of Industry and Information Technology will establish a list of green factories in a dynamic management manner from 2022, and provide corresponding policy preferences or financial rewards to enterprises after they are rated. Green factories are a model for future factory transformation. They are factories that achieve intensive land use, clean production, waste resource utilization and low-carbon energy. They focus on the greening of the production process. As of March 2023, 6 batches have been announced, and a total of 2,783 T factories have been recognized as green factories, involving multiple key energy-consuming industries such as textiles, steel, building materials, and chemicals.

The country has been vigorously developing green energy-saving enterprises and cultivating a large number of green strategic emerging enterprises. According to Tianyancha data, as of March 2023, there are more than 1.16 million green and low-carbon related enterprises in my country, of which 350,000 new registered enterprises were added in 2022, with a growth rate of 45.71%. In 2022, the annual revenue of the ecological and environmental protection industry was about 2.22 trillion yuan, an increase of about 1.9% over the same period in 2021. Although it was lower than the GDP

growth rate for the first time, more than 70% of enterprises are expected to maintain growth in operating revenue in 2023. Through years of strategic layout and vigorous promotion, my country has become a major country in energy conservation and new energy and renewable resource utilization in the world. In 2022, the total installed capacity of renewable energy in China exceeded 1.2 billion kilowatts, and the installed capacity of hydropower, wind power, solar power generation, and biomass power generation ranked first in the world. Among them, the installed capacity of wind power is about 370 million kilowatts, an increase of 11.2% year-on-year; the installed capacity of solar power generation is about 390 million kilowatts, an increase of 28.1% year-on-year. The coal-fired power units that can achieve ultra-low emissions exceed 1.05 billion kilowatts, accounting for about 94%[5].

New energy vehicles are booming. According to data from the China Association of Automobile Manufacturers, my country's new energy vehicles continued to grow explosively in 2022, with production and sales reaching 7.058 million and 6.887 million respectively, up 96.9% and 93.4% year-on-year respectively, ranking first in the world for eight consecutive years[6].

1.4 Green lifestyle has become popular

Green lifestyles are gradually being promoted in society, bringing positive social effects. On the one hand, members of society, mainly the government, pay more attention to the improvement of green living environment. In terms of green environment, in 2022, a total of 3.83 million hectares of afforestation, 3.214 million hectares of grass planting and improvement, and 1.8473 million hectares of desertified land were completed. Through the construction of national forest cities, national garden cities, and national forest villages, my country has increased the per capita park green space in cities from 11.8 square meters in 2011 to 14.78 square meters in 2021, and the village greening coverage rate has reached 32.01%. The urban and rural living environment has continued to improve. In terms of urban infrastructure construction, in 2022, 16,900 urban gas pipeline and other aging renovation projects

will be started nationwide, 22,000 kilometers of urban sewage pipe networks will be newly built and renovated, and the construction of urban underground comprehensive pipelines and sponge cities and the classification of domestic waste will continue to advance [7]. On the other hand, actions such as sorting of domestic waste, saving food and opposing waste, saving water and opposing excessive packaging of goods have been promoted in society and received positive responses from the public. Everyone actively participates and supervises each other, forming a good social atmosphere, and a green, environmentally friendly, civilized and healthy lifestyle has become the conscious choice of more members of society.

2 Analysis of the mechanism by which green economy promotes the innovative development of green enterprises

2.1 Financial support for green enterprises from green economic development

Green economy can provide financial support for green enterprises and green technology innovation on a sustainable and large scale, which has a direct impact on green enterprises and will also subtly affect the financing direction of green enterprises. At the same time, green economic policies will adopt targeted funding, so green enterprises will inevitably tend to green technology innovation and green products in their decision-making. Green industry products and services cannot generate direct economic benefits in the initial stage of green technology innovation, so there are problems such as large investment, long payback period and high risk. Compared with the green economy, the profit orientation of ordinary economic financing is difficult to guide enterprises to allocate more resources to green innovation projects, which is also one of the characteristics of the green economy. Therefore, under the guidance of green economic policies, economic institutions will inevitably adjust the direction of funds according to the policy direction, so that green enterprises' green innovation projects can obtain continuous financial support [8]. With the in-depth development of the green economy, the green economy will gradually gain support from laws, regulations, systems, the overall environment and other aspects, thereby driving the in-depth development of the demand for green products and green services. The profitability of green projects will gradually increase, thereby attracting more investment institutions to participate, and further enriching the relevant products and services of the green economy, such as green insurance and green bonds, promoting broader financing channels for green enterprises, and forming a virtuous circle between the green economy and green enterprises.

2.2 Green economic development accelerates enterprises' green transformation

Green economy can also guide the adjustment of industrial structure, transform the development mode of traditional industries, promote their development towards green economy, and promote the development and growth of green economy and green industry. The rapid development of green economy will inevitably restrict the credit investment in traditional high-energy-consuming industries, which will inevitably restrict the

development of high-emission projects. In addition, green economy will inevitably force high-emission enterprises to find ways to carry out green innovation, vigorously develop green technology, and tilt resource allocation towards green equipment. In addition, green economy can also provide green enterprises with more diversified products, support their related innovation projects, and attract more social investment to participate, which will reduce the financing pressure of enterprises to a certain extent, encourage green enterprises to carry out technological innovation, and provide consumers with more abundant green products and services.

2.3 Green economic development sends signals to green enterprises

In 2020, China has clearly proposed to achieve the "dual carbon" goal, vigorously develop the green economy, and realize the transformation of the green industrial structure, precisely to achieve the "dual carbon" goal. At present, all of China's policies are oriented towards developing a green economy and achieving environmental sustainable development. Therefore, these have sent a positive and strong signal to green enterprises and the green economy -green and low-carbon are the basic principles for obtaining economic and policy support. On the contrary, high-energy-consuming enterprises must accept relatively strict financing conditions, as well as various tax penalties and high interest rates under non-compliant and high-carbon operations that are not conducive to the development of enterprises. These are bound to serve as a warning to other market players from the side, and they should speed up the transformation and embark on the path of green innovation. At the same time, social investors often join the green industry based on the direction of policy signals and the direction of profits, and promote related enterprises to actively carry out green innovation and provide more high-quality green products to the society.

2.4 Porter hypothesis and innovation compensation theory

According to green economic theory, green industries often have long cycles, high risks, and uncertain returns. Therefore, the green innovation investment of enterprises will inevitably reduce the funds needed for normal production and operation of enterprises, thus generating negative impacts. However, the famous Porter hypothesis puts forward a completely different view, arguing that with the development and growth of the green economy, relatively mature green economic systems, laws and regulations will inevitably promote green enterprises to actively carry out green technological innovation, and reduce pollutant emissions and reduce the damage to the environment caused by product production by improving production processes and production techniques. The reason is that new technologies and new processes can reduce the investment of enterprises in environmental governance [9]. In addition, with the output of high-quality green products and green services, the core competitiveness of green enterprises is constantly increasing, thus creating a more systematic and scientific green economic system for green enterprises. Relatively speaking, the benefits of

green innovation are absolutely greater than the investment in green transformation. In other words, "innovation compensation" can actually greatly reduce the cost investment of green enterprises and comprehensively improve the benefits of green enterprises. This is beneficial to the development of green enterprises.

2.5 Global Moran's I index of regional green economic development level

The global Moran's Index (Moran's I) was used to calculate the average spatial agglomeration of 29 provinces in China in terms of green investment, government support, and carbon economy. A 29x29 first-order proximity matrix was calculated using the Queen neighbor method, and the matrix was used as a spatial weight matrix to quantify the spatial relationship between provinces. The specific results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Global Moran's I index of regional green economic development level from 2012 to 2023; Source: [10]

years	Green Investment	Government support	Carbon Economy
2012	0.202 *	0.256*	0.393**
2013	0.285**	0.218*	0.386**
2014	0.246*	0.156	0.387**
2015	0.332**	-0.015	0.375**
2016	0.249**	0.071	0.370**
2017	0.118	0.024	0.339**
2018	0.134	-0.194	0.339**
2019	0.301**	0.157	0.330**
2020	0.197*	0.017	0.322**
2021	0.233*	0.266*	0.328**
2022	0.081	-0.047	0.332**
2023	0.324**	-0.162	0.327**

It can be seen from Table 1 that the global Moran's I index of the carbon economy is all above 0.3, and all pass the 1% significance level test, indicating that there is a significant spatial correlation between the development level of the carbon economy. The overall Moran's I index of green investment is mostly above 0.2. To a certain extent, it can be considered that the development level of green investment also has a significant spatial correlation. Although the government support variable also has a certain spatial correlation in individual years, the overall spatial correlation is weaker than the other two dimensional variables.

3. Policy recommendations for green economy to promote the innovative development of green enterprises

The green economy wants to develop in an in-depth direction, it must make strategic arrangements from the top design level such as policies and systems. The author believes that this can be done from the following six aspects.

3.1 Improve and perfect the laws, regulations and policies related to green economy

From a strategic perspective, we should comprehensively grasp the positive impact of green economy on the development of green enterprises and form an accurate understanding of green economy. We should build a sound legal system to lay a solid foundation for the standardized development of green economy market: we should build a systematic green economy policy and legal system, and timely rectify the unreasonable aspects of green economy policy to meet the requirements of green economic development: we should adapt to local conditions, accurately lock in the target, tailor policies for the development of green enterprises, pay dynamic attention to the implementation of policies, and escort the development of green enterprises: we should improve the relevant rules of green economy market, widely absorb social capital, make it join the

development highway of green economy, promote the rational and optimized allocation of green economy resources, and effectively solve the financing difficulties of green enterprises: we should strengthen the cooperation between economic institutions and social economic organizations, strengthen the control of investment risks, and work together to achieve the sustainable development of green enterprises.

3.2 Enrich and expand green economic tools.

Each region should base itself on its own reality, continuously optimize green economic tools, actively promote green economic tools to local enterprises, make them fully aware of the effectiveness of green economic tools, and thus fully explore the market space for green economic tools. In view of the long payback cycle and high risk of green industries, each region should match appropriate green economic tools according to its own economic situation and enterprise development stage. Green enterprises using different levels of green economic tools should be treated equally, without discrimination against legal economic entities.

3.3 Encourage enterprises to pursue green and innovative high-quality development

All regions should actively encourage enterprises to carry out green innovation and create favorable conditions for the long-term sustainable development of enterprises. Green industries and green innovations are generally restricted by the characteristics of industries and sectors, especially green innovations that require long-term investment. Therefore, local governments should take measures according to local conditions, provide more precise economic services to green enterprises based on the development of green enterprises, the development direction and characteristics of green innovation, so as to fully stimulate the green innovation momentum of green enterprises. Take practical measures to encourage social capital to lean towards green enterprises, guide investment entities to better

identify green enterprises through green standards and other measures, and promote the green economy to flow to more high-quality green enterprises, laying a solid foundation for the rapid development of China's green economy.

3.4 Deepen the standardization of green innovation

At present, there are no formal recognition and disclosure standards for green innovation investment and effectiveness of green enterprises. Most people still confuse green R&D investment with ordinary innovation investment, which leads to increased support costs for economic institutions because they cannot allocate resources to green enterprises efficiently and accurately. In this case, segmentation measures can be set based on the details of human resources, funding sources, and other relevant characteristics of green industries and their products and services, and the relevant situation of green innovation R&D can be included in the audit, so as to guide and stimulate green enterprises to actively disclose their green innovation, so that green economic institutions can quickly identify high-quality green enterprises. Use third-party institutions for identification to ensure that the relevant information of green enterprises is reliable.

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

Nature provides humans with all kinds of resources, but humans use technology to destroy the ecosystem. Humans continue to exploit the economic value of nature, sell natural resources as commodities, and mix commercial interests with ecological protection. Humans have transitioned from agricultural civilization to industrial civilization, which has destroyed the relationship between man and nature and threatened human survival. It is necessary to further develop into an ecological civilization. Ecological civilization must develop a green economy and a knowledge economy to promote sustainable development of mankind. This article studies the development of China's green economy and draws the following conclusions.

1) Green economy can produce more products with limited resources. Green economy recognizes the limited nature of natural resources, takes into account the value of natural resources themselves, avoids damaging the inherent balance of natural ecology, and produces negative ecological effects. The ecological crisis forces humans to choose to develop a green economy to achieve a balance between economic development and ecological protection, and to achieve a combination of economic benefits, social benefits, and ecological benefits. Green economy advocates effective resource management and reduced waste. By promoting a circular economy, advocating renewable energy and sustainable agriculture, resources can be used more efficiently, their lifespan can be extended, and overexploitation of limited resources can be reduced. By reducing air and water pollution, improving urban planning, and providing better public transportation, the green economy helps improve people's quality of life and promotes good health.

2) Ecological problems have become a global problem, and China has also suffered greatly from it. Although China has made progress in the development

of renewable energy, it still faces a high dependence on fossil fuels. Coal remains China's main source of energy, which has a negative impact on air quality and greenhouse gas emissions. Although China has introduced a series of environmental protection regulations, there are still challenges in implementation. Some companies may not have enough motivation or face insufficient supervision, resulting in poor implementation of environmental protection regulations. China's green economy has problems such as ecological disharmony, insufficient interest driving force, unbalanced international relations, wrong ideology, inefficient mechanisms, and incomplete systems. It is necessary to improve the market mechanism, government system, ethical mechanism and ecological mechanism, and develop green enterprises, green finance, green procurement, green consumption, etc. The development of the green economy is a systematic project, which requires the coordination of various systems to reduce development costs.

3) The green economy needs to be driven by multiple mechanisms. It needs to strengthen the leading role of the market mechanism, give play to the regulatory role of the government mechanism, use the moral mechanism to restrict the behavior of the subject, and reflect the inherent laws of the ecological mechanism. The ecological mechanism and the moral mechanism are beneficial supplements to the market mechanism. They are determined by China's national conditions and development stage and can achieve the combination of economic benefits, social benefits and ecological benefits. The green economy needs institutional innovation, give play to the guiding role of the government, and establish a green enterprise system, a green financial system, a green procurement system and a green consumption system. The mechanism that emphasizes market orientation can promote the green economy through incentives and systems. For example, establishing a carbon market, promoting the marketization of renewable energy, and establishing environmental taxes can make green industries more competitive and stimulate enterprises to innovate for sustainable development. The government plays the role of regulator and guide in the green economy. The government can guide enterprises to develop in an environmentally friendly and sustainable direction through means such as formulating laws and regulations, setting environmental standards, providing financial support and incentives. The government can also promote the development of the green economy by building green infrastructure and promoting the research and development of new technologies.

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